

The Gaussian cycloid2

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The parameters generating the classical unit cycloid

$$x(t) = t - \sin(t)$$

$$y(t) = 1 - \cos(t) = x'(t)$$

are plotted below for one arch; in OCTAVE code, **r=.001;,t=0:r:2*pi;,y=1-cos(t);,x=t-sin(t);**

Thus the abscissa function is an increasing curve, while the bell-shaped ordinate is its derivative.

Let's work backwards: starting with a 'bell' curve as $y(t)$, generate an abscissa $x(t)$ as $\int y(t)$; plotting these two should yield a new cycloid. In OCTAVE, do

r=.001;,t=0:r:2*pi;,y=1-cos(t);,x=r*cumsum(y); not surprisingly, the results are identical.

Furthermore, for the area

$$A = \int_0^{2\pi} y(t) dx(t)$$

the simple OCTAVE command **r*y*y'** yields **9.424777960769378** $\cong 3\pi$. As for the arc-length

$$L = \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{x'(t)^2 + y'(t)^2} dt$$

the OCTAVE command

max(cumsum(sqrt(diff(x).^2 + (diff(y)).^2)))

gives **7.999999988386319**, not identical but numerically very close to the expected 8.

Now, a natural choice for the ordinate $y(t)$ is the Gaussian bell: $y(t) = \exp(-t^2)$; in OCTAVE do

r=.001;,t=-pi:r:pi;,y=exp(-t.^2);,x=r*cumsum(y);

The top two tiers show the parametrics; underneath, the Gaussian cycloid has indeed emerged.

The new digital parametrics are

$$y(t) = \exp(-t.^2);$$

$$x(t) = r * \text{cumsum}(y);$$

and the usual OCTAVE code for the area $r * y * y'$ yields **A = 1.253314136901946**; the arc-length command **max(cumsum(sqrt(diff(x).^2 + (diff(y)).^2)))** gives **L = 2.843810991612600**.

Orthogonality failed for the Gaussian cycloid as well; still, Gram-Schmidt complements devised previously **[1]**, yielded

$$z(t) = y(t) - kx(t), \text{ where } k = (x * y') / (x * x') = \mathbf{0.182322513441860}$$

and

$$w(t) = x(t) - qy(t), \text{ where } q = (x * y') / (y * y') = \mathbf{1.253791948178728}$$

The resulting cycloids are tiered below, distorted in appearance as those for the classical arc.

References

[1] A. Cusmariu, Cycloids old and new, <https://zenodo.org/records/13751134>, 2014